

IMPORTANCE OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN INCREASING LEARNERS' MOTIVATION

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Annatatsiya: Maskur maqolada autentik materillarni ingliz tilini o'rganishdagi jarayonida qollashning samarali usullari haqida fikr olib borilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur masala bo'yicha misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar : sinfxondagi tadqiqot, ma'no, tushuncha, haqiqiy materiallar.

Annotation: This article provides authentic materials and their importance in increasing learners 'motivation. The article also gives example on this topic.

Keywords: classroom investigation, context, concept, real materials.

Аннотация: в этой статье представлены аутентичные материалы и их важность в повышении мотивации учащихся. в этой статье также приведены примеры по этой теме

Ключевые слова: расследование в классе, концепция, контекст, реальные материалы.

There is a now special concern in language teaching that the use of authentic materials is crucial to develop of learning processes. English language teaching needs a meaningful context. It means that student should get "beyond" the language. This idea suggests that should only know language but also do how to use in the real life situation. So, insufficiently using amount of authentic materials is the best way to increase students 'motivation in the learning context. Authentic materials are defined as any spoken and written materials which are not for pedagogical purposes. Graves contents that although teachers do not deserve right to choose the core materials, they have to enlarge their creativity how to make such materials more interesting. One of the attempt is creating their own additional materials. Moreover, task –based language teaching is now widely used in the towns in which focus of English learning process is the communicative language tasks that students need to perform. Consequently, authentic materials play a key in promoting task- based language learning since they connect the language used in the classroom with natural use of language outside of the classroom. (Nunan, 1991, cited in Oura, 2001)

Due to the technological innovations, the twenty-first century has witnessed vast changes in all steps of life. The new technology supported the current educational system and it gifted the present time educational system with a newfangled content. As a result, there have been several creations in the system of education and English

has no exception. The concept of teaching English has dramatically changed and the present generation of teachers as well as the learners depend more on the latest technology that gets a greater change in teaching and learning process. In the modern world, the teachers of English have been using a variety of teaching materials in order to satisfy the needs and interests of the learners. In this process, they also go for the authentic materials in addition to the prescribed textbooks with an aim to improve the standards of the learners and to develop their learners' language skills tremendously in the usual English learning process. According to Peacock (1997), there are some advantage of authentic Authentic materials are more motivating for students, even lower level students, than artificial materials". Furthermore, Briton states, "Authentic materials relate more closely to learners' need, for they build a connection between the language classroom and the outside world. The teachers have to use all the available authentic materials such as newspapers, magazines, story books, movies, radio, TV ads, songs, label products, bus or train timetables, realia like phones and dolls so that the learners show more interest towards their leaning. As authentic materials play a vital role in promoting the learners' learning and creates interests among learners to learn the English language in a natural way with proper motivation, the teachers of English should use these authentic materials in their day-to-day teaching profession. The present paper brings to light to the effective use of authentic materials by the teachers in the English language classrooms. For this purpose, this paper initially discusses the advantages of authentic materials in the education. Then this paper brings out the importance of the authentic materials that are used in the English language classrooms. Later, this paper emphasizes primarily on the effective use of the authentic materials and how they assist the teachers in their teaching and also how they help the learners to learn English in a better and easier way. Finally, this paper gives some expedient hints both to the teachers and the learners of English to how improve their teaching and learning skills colossally using the authentic materials in the learning context. In contemporary digital period, technology arrangeded a new dimension in almost all the fields and the field of education has highly benefitted in bringing tremendous changes in teaching and learning processes. With the introduction of the internet and computers in education, the teaching and learning has become easy an accessible for all the teachers and learners of English. The teachers have been using the internet to download materials, update their knowledge, get immediate solutions for their doubts and queries, show the required pictures, videos and audios to the learners, give Power Point presentations, record the learning process of the students and so on. After the introduction of the mobile phones or smart phones, there is a tremendous change in the learning style of the learners. The learners are able to learn the language both in and outside the classrooms. As the present generation of learners gets the opportunity

of using numerous sources to learn any subject, the use of authentic materials seems to be a great help for them to improve their learning skills. The teachers can use the authentic material as additional material to develop the overall skills of the learners' learning. With the help of the authentic material, the teachers can reinforce the

learning items and can give additional tasks to the learners. Furthermore, these authentic materials create interest among the learners since the teachers select them with proper care by taking the needs and interests of the learners. As a result, the learners can participate with more enthusiasm in the given tasks and try to perform the tasks with utmost care and concentration. Authentic materials are abundantly used in the teaching of English by the teachers to attain better results while teaching the learners in the English language classrooms.

The teaching is concept which is a subject commonly depends on the analysis of the nature of the certain subject, its teaching and learning system in research and the theories related to philosophy and psychology of education. Teaching learning materials continually handle methods, approaches materials, syllabus and evaluation. Language teachers use two types of materials, i.e., the materials that are exclusively get ready for teaching a language, for example textbooks and authentic materials such as newspapers, brochures, pamphlets, etc. that are used for the purposes other than teaching but are often used in the language classrooms while they teach a language. The materials used in the classroom are precisely prepared by the subject experts of the English language to meet the needs and requirements of the learners. Even though these materials provide standard information, they are monotonous. In motivating the learners, the materials adapted by the subject experts and they fail to present the realworld or situational language and it leads to teachers' burnout. Therefore, it is more essential for the language teachers to prepare their own materials for their teaching according to the needs and interests of the learners and also according to the demands of the prevailing society. As the normal and prescribed materials do not satisfy the needs and interests of the students, the teachers of English have to prepare some supplementary materials on their own. In this meaning, authentic materials are so useful for them to use in their classrooms. The teachers of English can adopt materials on the needs of the learners so that the learners can work on the given materials with a lot of interest and more enthusiasm. Indeed, authentic materials provide very good resources for teachers and they give the learners an chance to expose to the real-life and out-of-classroom contexts. The main focus of the authentic materials in the learning context is to convey the meaning of the message and to communicate the message according to the context. When authentic materials are provided for the students, no hesitation, they will surely use English in real-life situations. Moreover, the learners develop their language skills huge and

communicate not only with their peers in the classrooms but also with friends, family members and other people outside the classrooms.

Reference:

1.Cornish, S. (2014), Video in the TESOL Classroom, in Erica Garvey's reading text for language teaching methodologies, NCELTR, Macquarie University, Sydney- Australia, p: 25

2.Crawford, J. (2015), the Role of Materials in the Language Classroom: Finding the balance, in the Erica Garvey's reading text for Language Teaching Methodologies, NCELTR, p: 28-31

3.Garvey, E. (2007), Lecture 3: Materials and Resources, Language Teaching Methodologies, NCELTR, Macquarie University-Sydney, Australia, p: 2

4.Guariento, W. and Morley, J. (2001), Text and Text Authenticity in the EFL classroom, ELT Journal; Oxford University Press in association with the British Council, volume 55/4, p: 347, 348, 349 and 351

5.Hanson-Smith, E. (2001), Computer Assisted Language Learning in the text of: The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages, by Carter, Rand Nunan D, p: 109, 110

6. Larimer, R. E. and Schleicher, L. (2000), New Ways in Using Authentic Materials in the Classroom, TESOL Inc., p: introduction section, 21, 52, 102, 148, 158, 166

7. Linder, D. (December 1999/January2000), Authentic Texts in ESL/EFL, TESOL Matters, 9:6, p: 17, from the website: [readwriteact.org /files /2013/ 02/ authentic_texts_in_esl_efl.pdf](http://readwriteact.org/files/2013/02/authentic_texts_in_esl_efl.pdf) accessed on 04.04.2013

